

International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research (IJHRIR)

ISSN: 2349 –3593 (Online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-3-july-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

COMPARISON OF JOB SATISFACTION OF TEACHING AND NON-TEACHING STAFF IN AN ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS CASE STUDY ON ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY (INDIA)

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Abstract:

For any academic organization job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching staff is considered essential for its success of any academic institution. When teachers are satisfied the over-all efficiency and quality of an academic institution increases while satisfaction of non-teaching staff such as clerk, lab attendant, librarian, placement officer etc act as a supporting factor for academic organization quality. Therefore it is mandatory to know the determinants of job satisfaction for teaching and non-teaching employs of an academic institution. For the same reason study was undertaken determine the factors driving satisfaction of teachers and non-teaching staff of Aligarh Muslim University, India. In this paper primary data is used which is collected through survey method by using questionnaire form containing mostly structured questions from a sample size 100 (50 teaching and 50 non-teaching staff). The research also shows that the overall job satisfaction of teachers gets affected by satisfaction level of non-teaching staff and monthly income is directly proportional to the degree of job satisfaction for both, teaching and non-teaching staff.

Key Word: Job satisfaction, teachers, non-teaching staff, performance, academic organizations.

Introduction:

All the employees of an academic institution can be broadly classified as teaching and non-teaching staff. Teaching profession is one of the noblest and most respected professions from the very beginning of human civilization. This is because, students are considered as future of a nation and it is teacher's duty to guide and help in development of knowledge and skills in students. So the job satisfaction of teachers results in their improved performance. In any academic organization there is synchronized working of teaching and non-teaching staff. Therefore for the achievement of goal and increase productivity, both teaching and non-teaching staff should function in synchronized way, which is achieved when there is mental state of job satisfaction among both groups of employees. As both groups of employees interacts in various day to day activities, a relationship is developed between them and satisfaction or dissatisfaction one group impact indirectly or indirectly on other group. By academic organization here it means schools, collage and research institutes.

Meaning and Concept of Job Satisfaction:

In general, Job satisfaction refers to the extent to which employees gain enjoyment from their effort at the work place. Job satisfaction can be influenced by the person's ability to complete the task, the communication in an organization and the way management treats employees. Job satisfaction refers to an over-all effective orientation on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying. Almost all the researchers defined job satisfaction as the fulfillment of one's expectation related to his/ her job. Job satisfaction is subjective in nature and varies from person to person. Job satisfaction for one person may differ partially or completely from job satisfaction of other person. It is due to the determinant of job satisfaction may differ from person to person. Such as in the present case determinant of job satisfaction for teacher may be level of education, monthly salary, recognition, success of his/her students, respect gained by students etc. While for non-teaching staff, determinant of job satisfaction may be monthly salary, working condition, job security, organizational policies etc.

Statement of Problem:

In India education is an important factor for the growth and development of an individual as well as for the development of whole nation to fight against poverty and unemployment. There are many nations (mostly third-world nations) which are trying to fight poverty and unemployment by using education as a tool. So focusing on educational/academic field is required more now days. There are many researches already done for finding out determinant of job satisfaction in general (Oshagbemi, 2003; Lu et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2006; Horton, 2006); There are many researches done solely related to job satisfaction of teaching profession (Bishay, A 1996; Michaelowa, K 2002; Mwamwenda, T. S 1997) and there are researches focusing on job satisfaction of clerical and office jobs(Dix, C and Brain, C 1988; Veli-Matti Höynälä 2009). However less attention is paid on both the groups of an academic organization together. Also there is less attention paid on the effect of satisfaction/dissatisfaction of one group on working and productivity of other group. Therefore in order to find and analyze the determinant of job satisfaction both groups of employees and their effect on one another.

Significance of the Study:

This paper throws light on the determinant of job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching employees working together in school, collage or research institute. This research paper also deals with finding-out the effect of satisfaction of one group on other group. The research of this paper will allow better understanding of factor causing job satisfaction of teachers as well as non-teaching staff of an organization which is considered as one of the most important factor for increasing quality and productivity of academic organizations.

Literature Review:

- Hoppock's (1935), seminal study of job satisfaction revealed that dissatisfaction with wages was the most important reason advanced for voluntary separation across a broad array of occupations.
- Herzberg (1957) has shown that more satisfied workers will tend to add more value to an organization. Unhappy employees, who are motivated by fear of job loss, will not give 100 percent of their effort for very long.
- Herzberg (1959), different factors combine to create job satisfaction and dissatisfaction among employee. He identified and classifies these factors as , motivation and hygiene factors. Motivators promote job satisfaction. They include: (a) achievement, (b) responsibility, (c) the work itself, (d) recognition, and (e) advancement/promotion. Hygiene factors do not directly lead to job satisfaction among employees. However, their absence may lead to job dissatisfaction. They consist of: (a) organizational policies, (b) supervision and leadership, (c) pay or salary, (d) work conditions, (e) communication with

supervisors/work partners.****According to Herzberg, employers should adopt ways of eliminating dissatisfaction resulting from hygiene factors and focus on improving the motivators in the work environment in order to increase employ job satisfaction.

- Blum and Naylor (1968), found that job satisfaction is the result of various attitudes possessed by an employee. In a narrow sense, their attitudes are related to the job and are concerned with specific factors such as steadiness of employment, wages supervision, working condition, recognition of potential, advancement opportunities, fair evaluation of task, social relations on job, quick settlement of grievances, and fair treatment by employer and similar other items.
- Michael R. Carrell and Norbert F. Elbert (1974), they found that there was inverse relationship between education level and satisfaction, with the college graduates being the least satisfied and those with less than a high school diploma being the most satisfied. Clerks with an urban home environment were less satisfied than those with rural home environment. In addition, location was found to have a significant main effect.
- Perie & Baker (1979), in their study concluded that the job satisfaction teacher may be directly related to the student achievement.
- Ramkrishnaiah (1980), in his study he found that about 93 percent of highly satisfied college teachers have cordial relationship with their colleagues.
- Ting (1997), in his study shows that job characteristics such as salary, promotional opportunity, task clarity and significance, and skills utilization, as well as organizational characteristics such as commitment and relationship with supervisors and co-workers, have significant effects on job satisfaction.
- Nwachukwu Prince Ololube (2006) concluded that factors of job satisfaction seem to have a greater impact on teaching performance.
- Shamima Tasnim (2006), found that one of the main objective of doing a job is to get the salary and it is quite usual that a handsome salary will cause job satisfaction of an employ.
- Bloch (2009), in his study found that academicians are more motivated, committed to perform their job and are also more satisfied if there are promotion opportunities for them.
- Mohamed Imran Rasheed (2010), found that the potential factors for satisfying teachers in higher education are recognition, work environment, job design, decision making, participation, feedback are the potential factor for satisfying teachers in higher education.
- Smt. Dipika R. Chaudhari (2012) suggested that teachers having positive and favorable attitude towards their profession are generally successful, properly adjusted and well satisfied with their job.
- Om Raj Katoch (2012) concluded that the teachers working on contract basis are dissatisfied with their job; and they should get at least the full salary benefits.

Objectives of the Study:

- 1) To know the determinant of job satisfaction of teaching staff and non teaching staff in Aligarh Muslim University.
- 2) To compare the determinant of job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching staff.
- 3) To know whether level of job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching staff are related to each other or not

Research Hypothesis:

The following research hypotheses were formulated to direct the study:

- 1) Hypothesis 1: Some of the factors causing job satisfaction are different for teaching staff and non-teaching staff of an academic organization.
This hypothesis is proposed to identify, analyze and compare those factors which cause job satisfaction in teaching staff but not in non-teaching staff and vice-versa.
- 2) Hypothesis 2: The monthly salary is the common determinant of job satisfaction for both groups of staff (i.e. teaching and non-teaching).

This hypothesis is proposed to find and analyze the effect of monthly salary in both the groups of staff.

- 3) Hypothesis 3: The degree of job satisfaction of one group of staff is either directly or inversely proportional to degree of the job satisfaction of another group of staff.

This hypothesis is proposed to find the relationship and effect of job satisfaction/ dissatisfaction of the other group of employ on another group.

Methodology:

This study is a cross sectional research. This study is based on empirical research methodology and involves collection of data by using questionnaire form which is filled by sample of teaching and non-teaching staff.

Sample Design: Aligarh Muslim University (A.M.U.) which a central university has more than 30 colleges and schools situated in Aligarh district only. Out of which 8 colleges and 2 schools were selected by using convenience sampling i.e. total 10 academic institutions. Then out of each of the selected academic institution 5 samples from teaching staff and 5 samples of non-teaching staffs were selected by using simple random sampling.

Area of Study: This study covers teaching staff and non-teaching staff of 8 colleges and 2 schools of A.M.U. in Aligarh district.

The colleges are; Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Dr. Ziauddin Ahmad Dental College, Abdullah Girls College, M.B.A. Department, Zakir Hussain College of Engineering and Technology, A.M.U. Polytechnic, Ajmal Khan Tibya College, K.A. Nizami Centre for Quranic Studies.

The schools are; S.T.S. High School and A.M.U. Girls High School.

Data Collection Tool:

A questionnaire form was used for collecting data from selected colleges and school. The questionnaire form consists of three parts.

- The first part consists of question related to gender, designations, education, work experience, salaries, skills and abilities.
- The second part consists of overall job satisfaction level which is rated by a sample respondent by using Likert Scaling.
- The third part consists of various factors related to job satisfaction. In this part Constant Sum Scaling method is used. Total 100 points were given to respondent then they were asked to allocate points to those factors.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The analysis of primary data and interpretation is done in three parts to test hypothesis, shown as following:

HYPOTHESIS 1: To test hypothesis 1, third part of questionnaire form were analyzed. In third part of questionnaire Constant Sum Scaling method was used. Respondent were given a constant sum of 100 points and then asked to allocate points to various factors causing job satisfaction. Greater the importance of factor, higher the score. Two separate tables are drawn one for teaching and one for non-teaching staff respondent, showing the total score allocated by respondents to a factor and the average value of score of that factor. Average value is calculated by dividing the total score of a factor by total number of respondent i.e. 50 in both cases. Then comparison is done of both average values of each job satisfaction factor.

TABLE 1.1
Score and Average value of Factors causing Job Satisfaction

(Sample Respondent – Teaching Staff)

Factors of Job Satisfaction	Total Score	Average
Hours worked each week	135	2.7
Flexibility in schedule	122	2.44
Amount of paid vacation time	183	3.66
Sick leave offered	180	3.6
Salary	415	8.3
Opportunities for Promotion	389	7.78
Benefits (Health insurance, life insurance, etc.)	364	7.28
Job Security	465	9.3
Recognition for work accomplished	318	6.36
Healthy Relationships with teaching staff.	372	7.44
Healthy Relationship with non-teaching staff.	261	5.22
Relationship with supervisor/ HOD/ Principle	342	6.84
Opportunity to utilize skills and talents	380	7.6
Opportunity to learn new skills	353	7.06
Support for additional training and education	291	5.82
Success of Students	430	8.6
TOTAL	5000	100

Primary Data

TABLE 1.2
Score and Average value of Factors causing Job Satisfaction
(Sample Respondent – Non-Teaching Staff)

Factors of Job Satisfaction	Total Score	Average
Hours worked each week	390	7.8
Flexibility in schedule	402	8.04
Amount of paid vacation time	200	4
Sick leave offered	388	7.76
Salary	408	8.16
Opportunities for Promotion	375	7.5
Benefits (Health insurance, life insurance, etc.)	132	2.64
Job Security	479	9.58
Recognition for work accomplished	307	6.14
Healthy Relationships with teaching staff.	277	5.54
Healthy Relationship with non-teaching staff.	395	7.9
Good Relationship with supervisor/ HOD/ Principle	264	5.28
Opportunity to utilize skills and talents	229	4.58
Opportunity to learn new skills	293	5.86
Support for additional training and education	302	6.04
Success of Students	159	3.18
TOTAL	5000	100

Primary Data

Findings: On comparing the average value and total score of each factors (from first table) with the average value and total score of same factor (from second the tables), it was found that:

- 1) There are some factors which causes job satisfaction in both the group of samples. These factors are Amount of paid vacation time, Monthly Salary, Opportunity of Promotion, Job Security, Recognition for Work Accomplished. The average value of these factors shows a slight variation if compared in both tables.

- 2) There are some factors which causes job satisfaction in only teaching staff sample and not in non-teaching staff sample. The total scores and average values of these factors are more in teaching staff sample table. These factors are Success of Students, Opportunity to learn new skills, Opportunity to utilize skill, good relationship with supervisor/HOD/principal, healthy relationship with teaching staff and benefits like health insurance and life insurance.
- 3) There are some factors which causes job satisfaction only in non-teaching staff sample and not in teaching staff sample. The total scores and average values of these factors are more in non-teaching staff sample table. These factors are; hours worked each day, flexibility in schedule, sick leave offered and healthy relationship with non-teaching staff.

Result: The above findings conforms that some of the factors causing job satisfaction are different for teaching staff and non-teaching staff of an academic organization. Therefore Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

HYPOTHESIS 2: To test hypothesis 2, the teaching and non-teaching staff sample respondent was separated. Then the following series of steps were performed for both the groups separately:

- 1) The sample respondents are categorized on the basis of monthly income in different class and the number of sample respondent in each class was noted, as shown in table 2.1 & table 2.2.
- 2) Then part II of questionnaire form was analyzed in which Likert scale rating was use to rate the overall satisfaction level. Then the sum of rating of overall satisfaction level for each class was done.
- 3) Then the average value of overall satisfaction level for each class is calculated by dividing the sum of rating of overall satisfaction level of that class by the number of sample respondents of that class respectively.

Table 2.1
Sample Respondent According to their Monthly Income;
Teaching Staff

MONTHLY INCOME (in Rupees)	NUMBER OF TEACHING STAFF SAMPLE RESPONDENT	SUM OF OVERALL SATISFACTION RATING	AVERAGE VALUE OF OVERALL JOB SATISFACTION
Above 80000	24	116	4.83
60000-80000	11	48	4.36
40000-60000	8	31	3.87
20000-40000	7	23	3.28
Up to 20000	0	0	0

Primary Data

Table 1.2
Sample Respondent According to their Monthly Income;
Non-Teaching Staff

MONTHLY INCOME (in Rupees)	NUMBER OF TEACHING STAFF SAMPLE RESPONDENT	SUM OF OVERALL SATISFACTION RATING	AVERAGE VALUE OF OVERALL JOB SATISFACTION
Above 80000	0	0	0
60000-80000	3	13	4.33
40000-60000	19	71	3.73
20000-40000	20	68	3.40
Up to 20000	8	23	2.87

Primary Data

Findings:

- 1) From Table 2.1: The highest paid monthly salary to the teaching staff sample respondent is above Rs 80000 and this class has highest average value of overall job satisfaction i.e. 4.83. The class of lowest paid monthly salary to the teaching staff sample respondent is Rs 20000-40000 and this class has lowest average value of overall job satisfaction, i.e. 3.28.
- 2) From Table 2.2: The highest paid monthly salary is Rs 60000-80000 and this class has highest average value of overall job satisfaction, i.e. 4.33. The class of lowest paid monthly salary is up to Rs 20000 and this class has lowest average value of overall job satisfaction, i.e. 2.87.
- 3) For both, teaching and non-teaching sample respondent as we move down from class with higher monthly salary to the class of lower monthly salary, the average value of overall satisfaction decreases.

Result: On analyzing the average value of overall job satisfaction of both the groups of respondent, it can be clearly noted that in both the groups of sample respondent with higher monthly salary has more overall job satisfaction level and as the monthly income of sample respondent decreases the overall job satisfaction also decreases.

Therefore the Hypothesis 2 is accepted i.e. the monthly salary is the common determinant of job satisfaction for both groups of staff (i.e. teaching and non-teaching).

HYPOTHESIS 3: To test hypothesis 3, the sample respondent were classified on the basis of collage/school in which they work, there were 8 collages and 2 schools which were selected by convenient sampling. Then for each collage/school the average value of overall job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching sample respondent were calculated respectively (as in Table 3.1).

Average value of overall job satisfaction is calculated by dividing the sum of overall job satisfaction rating by number of sample respondent.

Table 3.1
Average Values of Overall Job Satisfaction of Sample Collages and Schools

SAMPLE COLLAGES AND SCHOOLS	AVERAGE VALUE OF OVERALL JOB SATISFACTION	
	TEACHING SAMPLE RESPONDENT	NON-TEACHING SAMPLE RESPONDENT
Jawaharlal Nehru Medical Collage	4.1	4.0
Abdullah Girls Collage	3.6	3.7
Dr. Ziauddin Ahmad Dental Collage	2.8	2.5
M.B.A. Department, A.M.U.	3.9	3.8
Zakir Hussain Collage of Engineering and Technology	4.5	4.4
A.M.U. Polytechnic	4.7	4.8
Ajmal Khan Tibya Collage	3.0	2.9
K.A. Nizami Centre for Quranic Studies	2.2	2.1
S.T.S. High School, A.M.U.	3.3	3.6
Girls High School, A.M.U.	4.2	4.0

Primary Data

Findings: On comparing the average value of overall job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching sample respondent each sample collage and school, it was found that:

- 1) The collage and school having higher average value of overall job satisfaction of teaching sample respondent, have higher value of overall job satisfaction of non-teaching staff and vice-versa. e.g. in case of Jawaharlal Nehru Medical Collage the average values of overall job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching staff are 4.1 and 4.0 respectively.
- 2) In case of collages and school having lower average value of overall job satisfaction of teaching staff, have lower average value of overall satisfaction of non-teaching sample respondent and vice-versa.
- 3) The difference between the average values is very small e.g. In case of K.A. Nizami Centre for Quranic Studies the difference between the average values of overall job satisfaction is 0.1, Girls High School, A.M.U.

Result: The level of overall job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching sample respondent is directly related to each other. If the overall job satisfaction of teaching sample respondent is high the overall job satisfaction of non-teaching staff will also be high. Therefore Hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Conclusion:

- In this study many factors affecting job satisfaction of teaching and non teaching staff of an academic institution were identified and analyzed by which we can conclude that there are some common factors and some different factors of job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching staff.

- Monthly income is one of the common factors that are acting in both types of employee. Handsome salary results in more job satisfaction of employee.
- The degree job satisfaction of either teaching or non-teaching staff has a directly related to other group's job satisfaction. The reason behind is, both the groups contributes in working environment of one another and working environment directly affect the job satisfaction of both the academically sound collage groups.

Suggestions: For increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of any academic institution it is mandatory to develop feeling of job satisfaction in teaching staff as well as in non-teaching staff too. To do so proper facilities should be provided by administration to all teaching and non-teaching staff, such as job security and opportunity of promotion etc. It should also be considered that there are some common factors of job satisfaction while some of the factors of job satisfaction differ. So a special care about those factors should be taken which differs for the two groups, such as working hours per week and flexibility in schedule causes job satisfaction in non-teaching staff but not in teaching staff. This philosophy should be changed that the development of properly functioning and or school depends only on the teaching staff. The role of monthly salary is very important in development of job satisfaction in either group of staff. The management should take a great care of work experience and educational qualification in deciding the monthly salary of an employ. If it is not done properly it might lead to dissatisfaction.

By considering all the above points, an administration can successfully develop satisfaction in its staff and can use their potential to maximum level. This will cause development of more efficient academic institution. This will ultimately result in betterment of society by providing more capable, knowledgeable and skilled students to society.

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